

Effect of guided reading strategies on the motivation of the students ...

Effect of guided reading strategies on the motivation of the students to increase reading skill of elementary level students in the subjects of English

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Abstract

The study investigated the Effect of guided reading strategies on the motivation of the students to increase reading skill of elementary level students in the subjects of English. The major objectives of the study were as follows: (i) to find out effectiveness of motivation before reading.(ii) To find out effectiveness of motivation during reading. (iii) to find out effectiveness of motivation after reading. This study was experimental in nature and the posttest only equivalent groups design was used. The population of the study constituted all the elementary school students studying English in grade three. A group of sixty students of grade three with equal reading difficulties was selected as the sample of the study through purposive sampling from Govt girl's higher secondary school Attock oil refinery (AOC). The sample students were further divided into experimental and control groups through random sampling technique. Motivation to Read Survey scale" was used for the collection of the data on motivation. Chi Square was applied to measure Motivation to Read Survey Scale. They study concluded that guided reading strategies had positive effect on students motivation to read. It is recommended that curriculum developers be include guided reading strategies while designing for primary school children curriculum. This study is significant for curriculum developer, policy makers, teacher and students.

Keywords: Guided Reading Strategies, Motivation, Reading Skill, Elementary Level

Introduction

Guided reading instructions carry on with modification of experience. To turn out to be more effective readers, students need the chance to practice reading and also incorporate listening, screening, and speaking skills. The needs and abilities of students are so different that it is essential for students to receive more individualized attention during reading instruction.

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Reading involves both decoding words and comprehending them, and students need the chance to practice both of these skills. Guided reading is an opportunity for teachers to differentiate instruction for students and to offer a closer examination of a text that cannot be done in a whole group setting. Proper guided reading instructions can help students understand and respond to the reading. Students are being asked to explore texts more thoroughly, using text evidence to support their answers. These teacher-led instructions happen daily to weekly, with activities proceeding before, during, and after reading a text. Groups are generally shaped based on student needs and abilities. In the early classes, lessons are developed, focusing on a particular skill. Word study, sight words, understanding of text features, and comprehension are all emphasised more in guided reading phonics. The skills and lessons are reinforced through a variety of texts and multiple lessons. The goal of guided reading instruction is to offer students the opportunity to not only become familiar with reading skills and practices, but to give students a small group setting where they may not feel unsettled to take risks in reading.

Fountas and Pinnell (1996) stated that the purpose of guided reading is to provide students with strategies that they can use when reading. When students have these skills and strategies and teacher support, reading becomes fun for students using problem-solving strategies. Students focus mainly on constructing meaning. Research on reading has revealed that students' motivation to read is an important factor contributing to reading achievement (Torres & Kathrine, 2010). If teachers can increase student motivation to read, students may become proficient readers (Knoll & Christopher 2000). Reading proficiently is a truly significant skill for learning in school and outside. To learn new information and to function in society, students need to be able to read. Part of being an enduring learner is the ability to read and obtain new information. The International Reading Association's (2009) policy paper states, "The skill to process and use language efficiently is important for maintaining our democracy in the technological world of the future." Those who cannot process and use language are deprived of their civil rights, are unable to fully participate in society, and are starved of economic opportunities that affect their socioeconomic mobility. There is a well-established link between motivation to read and reading achievement (Unrau & Schlackman, 2006). Students who are extra motivated to read have been given time to read a variety of materials and read more often. If reading achievement can affect an individual's economic mobility and civil rights, then it becomes important for educators to find the most successful ways to increase reading motivation in the classroom. If teachers can find ways to motivate students to read more and more frequently, increases in reading achievement should follow. Most elementary students give importance to reading but do not see reading as a positive or pleasurable activity. Reading is not a high priority for them. According to Gambrell (1996), the third-grade students in their study valued reading more than the fifth-grade students, and their study also suggests a decline in reading motivation as students get older. Evidence shows that early success in reading is the key to long-term success in school and in lifelong learning and that early intervention when reading problems arise is vital if long-term problems are to be avoided. Students who successfully learn to read in the early grades of school are well prepared to read for learning and for pleasure in the years to come. All teachers are familiar with the fact that success in school and all through life depends in large part on the ability to read. For teachers who teach very young children, this understanding is accompanied by both a professional and personal commitment to early reading success for all children. According to Shaaban and Kassim (2006), readers who give importance to

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reading and have positive self-concepts as readers are more likely to be expected to work harder at reading tasks than readers with negative attitudes and poor self-concepts. If students are not motivated to read and don't want to do it, then they have less of a possibility to succeed as readers. Guided reading instructions help and motivate children to read. Guided reading is an approach used by teacher to meet diverse instructional needs of all students in class room. The objective of Guided reading is not to teach a selected book but to teach them reading strategies they can apply to all books.

Statement of the Problem

This study was designed to find out effect of guided reading strategies on the motivation of the students to increase reading skill of elementary level students in the subjects of English.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were:

- I. To find out effectiveness of motivation before reading.
- II. To find out effectiveness of motivation during reading.
- III. To find out effectiveness of motivation after reading.

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant effect of guided reading strategies on students' motivation before reading.

Ho2: There is no significant effect of guided reading strategies on students' motivation during reading.

Ho3: There is no significant effect of guided reading strategies on students' motivation after reading.

Significance of the Study

This study will not only be helpful for teachers to understand the basic concept related to guided reading strategies but teachers also the teacher will be able to use it effectively and efficiently in their classroom situation. This current study will contribute in effective curriculum planning and design for reading instructions. Guided reading strategies may help teachers for developing reading skills in students to them enable them for lifelong learning and would help them in becoming independent reader.

Review of Related Literature

A student learning a second language cannot be likely to simply pick up a book and read it there are many components and strategies of reading that need to be taught, mainly when reading in a second language. One of the varieties of teaching methods is the guided reading method, in Pakistan a few teachers use guided reading strategies. Reading components are the basis of the vital goal of helping students to learn reading skill and for enduring learning. It is important to understand that nothing of the essential components of reading alone is enough. Therefore for increasing reading skill, all the components should teach using different, approaches, methods and strategies and teach all students to read correctly, rapidly, and with comprehension by the end of third grade.

Essential components of reading are: - Alphabetic is includes phonemic awareness, phonics, and decoding and this process is readers use to identify words. Readers must depend on

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knowledge of alphabetic and decoding skills to read strange words. Fluency is the ability to read with competence ease, speed and accuracy. Readers attend more to decoding than to understanding the meaning of what they are reading without fluency. When word and sentence reading are fluent and regular, readers can think more fully on understanding and linking sentences and paragraphs, which enables them to make meaning from the text.

Vocabulary is the organization of words whose meanings a individual knows and understands. Vocabulary knowledge specially, the breadth, depth, and flexibility of an individual's knowledge about words and it is a primary interpreter of reading success.

Reading comprehension is the product and process of understanding text, and needs a high level of meta-cognitive engagement with text.

Essential Components of Reading Instructions are:-

1. Phonemic awareness
2. Phonics
3. Vocabulary development
4. Reading fluency, including oral reading skills
5. Reading comprehension strategies

The guided reading (GR) approach includes the above recommended practices while clearly modeling the strategies. Research suggests that in guided reading small groups is an efficient way to improve primary school students' reading skills (Fountas and Pinnell, 1996). The approach was at first developed for reading skill revival of native English speaking students. According to Avalos (2007), guided reading approach for learner learning English as a second language (L2) has been an achievement in a low-socioeconomic district schools. Two classes took part in the study with modified guided reading teaching implemented daily for 30 minutes. In grade one, there were ten students who completed an average increase of 1.3 grade level in four months of implementation, and the other class had 13 students who complete an average 1.8 grade level increased within nine months of getting guided reading instruction.

Guided Reading is designed by teachers helping readers in their development of specific strategies meant to be increasing reading independence. Such strategies contain conclusion and assessing reading (Fisher, 2008). A basic feature of guided reading is the partition of sessions into three different phases that are before reading, during reading and after reading (Fountas & Pinnell, 1996). According to Fountas and Pinnell (1996) guided reading is "an instructional approach for supporting each learner's development of efficient strategies for processing new texts at gradually more challenging and difficulty levels". Lanning and LaMere (2000) acknowledged that the reason of guided reading is to help students in the acquiring of behaviors and the strategies of efficient and independent readers. Examples of some of the strategies of successful and independent readers comprise, making predictions, and comparing and contrasting (Foresman, 2004).

Guided Reading requires small group work in which learners are harmonized according to reading level. The function of the teacher in guided reading is important as they give differentiated instruction to go with each small group's reading level. Part of their role is to help readers in their development of strategies which aim to increase reading independence. Teachers help students' growing ability and as they make progress encourage the responsibility of gradually more challenging texts (Fountas & Pinnell, 2001).

According to Fountas and Pinnell (2012) guided reading empower learner' to decode as actively attending to the meaning of the text. Also, nature of intervention given to them and

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the matching of students reading' levels are helpful in forming groups the small group. Through conversation within groups can more improved understanding and the social interaction between students achieved. An important feature of guided reading is the partition of sessions into 3 clear phases: before reading, during reading and after reading (Fountas & Pinnell, 1996). These three phases are dividing into six steps of reading instruction, with an elective seventh step (Fountas & Pinnell, 2012). The steps of instruction are as follows:

1. Selection of text
2. Introduction to text
3. Reading the text silently or loud
4. Discussion of reading martial for comprehension text
5. Teaching points
6. Word work
7. Extending understanding

In present study three steps were used in reading strategies

Before Reading

When teacher first meet as a group, always it is important to make active the students' background information on what they will be reading in groups. This can be frequently done through a strategy or simply by making an idea with students' group. It is also significant to talk about main key vocabulary words before reading. It is also important to make predictions before reading. Predicting helps them read with a focus and prepare the learning environment for their learning.

During Reading

After the first stage, learners are now prepared to read for a reason. Students begin reading their assigned text and use the reading strategies continually. In classrooms, teachers have prepared reading comprehension materials and books for use in guided reading. Reading comprehension materials include precise comprehension and new strategy questions for the learners to answer. The teacher has also used reading strategies worksheets that are particularly guided reading worksheets and activities because time is an issue some times. These specific guided reading worksheets and activities are very useful in working on particular strategies with students. A final step during reading is having individual students read aloud to them separately from their group members. This helps the teacher measure their reading fluency and to make sure the text is suitable for their reading level.

After Reading

When students are completed reading in second step, and have completed their comprehension reading material or sheets, teacher has then do some enjoyable activities that narrate to reading strategies. Another choice is to take their understanding of the reading text farther by completing end of the book projects. A final choice give to learner is DEAR (Drop Everything and Read) time. Teacher fined it essential for students to self-select chosen reading books of their interest.

Motivation is related with the inspiration of momentum, or being motivated to take action (Ryan & Deci, 2000). People who are motivated follow activities positively, whether it is to perform a task to pass an academic subject or attain a personal objective. In motivational

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procedure, there are elements of choice, determination, and effort. Individuals may make a decision whether or not to follow a set goal, how long they will maintain activities related it, and how hard they will work regarding the attainment of their goal (Dornyei, 2000).

Research has exposed that different factors contribute in effective ways towards one's motivation to complete a specific task. These motivational factors inspire individuals with energy, importance, and endeavor to fulfill their own needs, needs, goals and self expectations, as well as the expectations of others like family, parents, friends etc (Dornyei & Otto, 1998). Reading, at a certain level, is involved with the skills and strategies needed in order to perform related tasks expertly, such as phonemic awareness,, word recognition, decoding skills, comprehension and vocabulary. On another equally significant level, it is involved with motivation, effort to fully learn and make use of the above skills and strategies (Wigfield, Gladstone, & Turci, 2016).

Cambria and Guthrie (2010) reveal that a student can have the skills to read, but without the motivation to read, he is not possible to become a good reader. Therefore, motivation should not be overlooked, in spite of whether a learner is developing reading skills in the first language which is L1 or second language which is L2. Although reading is usually understood as constructing meaning from written texts, it is more thoroughly outlined as a complex cooperative processes that skilled readers present when they read (Grabe, 2009). Reading includes a organization of lower level processes such as word recognition and implement knowledge of vocabulary, grammar as well as dialogue features, and higher level processes such as analysis, conclusion, understanding supervision, and critical evaluation (Grabe, 2009). Many general reading models have been designed since the 1970s to clarify what skilled reading demands. Such as Goodman (1976) and Smith (1971) dispute about Top down models that efficient reading is ideally impelled, and that a reliance on related information leads to more fluent reading (Stanovich, 1984).

However, for example, bottom up or data driven models, LaBerge and Samuels (1974) stressed on decoding skills and sustain that higher level processes must take place after lower level. Subsequently models such as Stanovich (1984) and Bernhardt (2011) explicate reading from an interactive balancing perspective, which suggest that higher level concept driven processes and lower level data driven processes coexist, facilitating each other regarding reading comprehension. At least two common reading models integrate the elements of affect. Help to set reader expectations and boost attention and perseverance in reading, Ruddell and Speaker's (1985) interactive model explains that affective factors such as interests, attitudes, and values can be used. Mathewson's (1994) affective model of reading specially determines motivation as a meaningful variable that could affect reading. This model find motivation along with attitude and other emotions as elements influencing a reader's decision to read, which further affect attention and comprehension method as well as recall, reflection, and application of reading. Nevertheless, neither model emphasis on motivational factors in specifically.

Reading motivation is typically describe from an educational psychology view rather than a language learning view point, and mainly it's require concepts and procedure drawn from motivation theories (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000). These include goal direction, competency of beliefs (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000) and task value (Gambrell, Palmer, Codling, & Mazzoni, 1996). Readers appear to have a tendency towards either a task master which is intrinsic orientation or a performance goal which is extrinsic orientation. An intrinsically motivated reader would be ambitious for reading for its own sake, while an extrinsically motivated

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reader would be motivated by external demands and values (Baker & Wigfield, 1999 & Wang & Guthrie, 2004). With regards to reading results, an aspiration for task master combine with a faith in one’s personal capacity to read is expected to result in determination and endeavor to read (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000).

Research Methodology

This study was experimental in nature. Guided reading strategies were independent variable and students’ motivation was dependent variable.

Population

The population of the study constituted all the elementary school students studying grade three English

Sample

A group of sixty students of grade three with equal reading difficulties was selected as the sample of the study through purposive sampling from Govt girl’s higher secondary school AOC. The sample students were divided into experimental and control groups through random sampling technique.

Instrument of the Study

The ‘Motivation to read Survey Scale” is a public-domain instrument and developed by Gambrell et al. (1996) was used. This scale provide, teachers with an efficient and reliable way to assess reading motivation qualitatively and quantitatively by evaluating students’ self-concept as readers and the value they place on reading. The motivation to read survey is Likert type scale. The Reading Survey instrument can be administered to an entire class, a small group, or an individual. This instrument consists of 20 items and uses a 4-point Likert type response scale. The survey assesses two specific dimensions of reading motivation: self-concept as a reader and value of reading. The items that focus on self-concept as a reader are designed to elicit information about students' self-perceived competence in reading and self-perceived performance relative to peers.

Administering the Motivation to Read Survey

The motivation to read survey combines group and individual assessment procedures. The motivation to survey can be administered to an entire class, small group, or individual. The survey was administered by the sample students of experimental group.

Interpretation of data

The data collected through Read to Motivation scale is analyzed and interpreted as under:

Table 1: - *Effect of guided reading strategies on student’s motivation before reading*

	statements	total	always	Almost always	Sometimes	never	χ^2	p value
1	I like discussing a book with a group of other students.	30	4	15	8	3	11.8	>.008
2	In my Guided Reading group, the discussion of the	30	9	13	7	1	10.00	>.019

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3	book is helpful when a book is introduced in my Guided Reading Group, It Fun	30	7	11	9	3	10.00	>.019
4	When I am in a Reading Group talking about stories, I always talk about my ideas	30	9	13	7	1	4.66	>0.19
5	I like when my teacher listens to me read	30	10	10	6	4	3.6	>.003

df= 3 χ^2 at 0.05=7.81

The above table indicates that the calculated value of χ^2 of statement no 1 was found to be 11.8, Calculated value of χ^2 of statement no 2 was found to be 10.00, the calculated value of χ^2 of statement no3 was found to be 10.00, the calculated value of χ^2 of statement no 4 was found to be 4.66, and the calculated value of statement no 5 χ^2 was found to be 3.6 and these values were higher than p value at 0.05 so the null hypothesis was rejected. It implies that there is significant effect of guided reading strategies on student's motivation before reading.

Table 2: - *Effect of guided reading strategies on student's motivation during reading*

	statements	total	always	Almost always	Sometimes	never	χ^2	p value
1	I like when my teacher listens to me read.	30	10	10	6	4	3.6	>.003
2	My friends think I am good reader	30	3	9	14	4	10.26	>.016
3	When I come to a word I don't know, I can figure it out	30	4	10	9	8	2.26	>.51

df= 3 χ^2 at 0.05=7.81

The above table indicates that the calculated value of χ^2 of statement no 1 was found to be 3.6, Calculated value of χ^2 of statement no 2 was found to be 10.26, the calculated value of χ^2 of statement no3 was found to be 2.26, were higher than p value at 0.05 so the null hypothesis was rejected. It implies that there is significant effect of guided reading strategies on student's motivation after reading.

Conclusion

The study concluded that guided reading strategies had a positive impact on students' motivation. There was a significant effect of guided reading strategies on students' motivation before reading, during reading, and after reading.

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Recommendation

The result of the study showed that there was a significant effect of guided reading strategies on the motivation of the students. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers may teach through guided reading strategies to increase the motivation of the students. Motivation should not be overlooked when learner is developing reading skills in a second language.

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